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Glossary of terms

Item	Description
IAM	Identity and Access Management
VRE	Virtual Research Environment
CCP	Cloud Computing Platform
HEU	Horizon Europe

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The Blue-Cloud project started in 2019, under the H2020 EU's research and innovation funding programme, with the aim of creating a European Open Science Cloud for marine data. This involves federating data and e-infrastructures to provide data products and technologies as open science resources for the wider marine research community. Since 2023, the Horizon Europe Blue-Cloud 2026 follow-up project has been advancing this pilot ecosystem into a Federated European Ecosystem. It delivers FAIR and open data, along with analytical services essential for progressing research on oceans, EU seas, and coastal and inland waters. Building on the foundations of the original Blue-Cloud project, the current technical framework remains open, extensible, and adaptable to the evolving needs of the marine research community.

The Blue-Cloud Virtual Research Environment (VRE) is a federation of computing platforms and analytical services, orchestrating computing and analytical services into integrated and managed applications exploiting federated Blue-Cloud data resources as well as external data resources. The VRE is built on the D4Science [1, 2] infrastructure and the gCube [3] open-source technology. From the end-user point of view, it manifests in the EOSC Blue Cloud2026 gateway (accessible at <https://blue-cloud.d4science.org>), the access point to the services and Virtual Laboratories available to the Blue-Cloud community.

In the context of the Blue-Cloud-2026 project, the VRE is expanded by bringing together multiple e-infrastructures computing resources and services for supporting the needs of the users with larger capacity and new services and features. This document describes the approaches to enable the federation of these new resources and services into the Blue-Cloud VRE, and reports on the currently federated infrastructures that are actively supporting the VRE: Google Cloud Platform and EGI Cloud Compute at INFN-Bari. The federation is achieved through three primary approaches: deploying JupyterHub on Kubernetes resources, either through managed services or Kubernetes set up on OpenStack by VRE operators, to provide access to single-user interactive applications such as Jupyter and RStudio; deploying Galaxy on Kubernetes to enable seamless execution of workflows; and utilizing the Cloud Computing Platform (CCP), which features a pluggable architecture supporting Docker-swarm and Galaxy as execution platforms, offering flexibility for diverse computational tasks.

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1. Blueprint for Infrastructure Federation in Blue-Cloud

1.1. Federation Model and Architecture

The Blue-Cloud VRE offers users with an integrated experience across all the applications available, as such, the federation of new resources must retain the seamless access independently of the location of the services or resources. Each participating site providing resources need to provide resources compatible with the deployment of the VRE Analytics Computing Framework services: either as OpenStack projects where the VRE operators can manage Virtual Machines or as Kubernetes clusters that support the execution of container-based applications. A minimum capacity of 256 CPU cores with 512 GB RAM and 10 TB persistent storage is recommended to join the Blue-Cloud VRE.

An additional federation option is considered for third-party services not part of the current Analytics Computing Framework. These can also be incorporated into the VRE offer as long as they are integrated with the Identity and Access Management (IAM) component to ensure a common identity and authorization across them. Integration with IAM uses the well-established OpenID Connect standard¹ which has support across multiple applications and application frameworks. For those applications that do not support OpenID Connect, a Policy Enforcement Point (PEP) proxy based on NGINX is available, so the authorization is managed externally to the application and still accessible to the VRE users.

Figure 1 shows the relevant components of the Blue-Cloud VRE and how the federation brings additional services and resources together.

¹ https://openid.net/specs/openid-connect-core-1_0.html

Figure 1 – Logical view of the Federation in the VRE

Users access the V Labs and services of the Blue-Cloud VRE Gateway, available at <https://blue-cloud.d4science.org/>. These are built on top of the Blue-Cloud VRE Core Services. The main integration point for the federation is by deploying the Analytics Computing Framework components, which includes JupyterHub², Galaxy³ and Analytics Engines, on the available federated resources. Direct access to the resources is not offered, these are always delivered through higher abstraction layers that facilitate their usage and integration in the VRE.

The resources can be either OpenStack projects where the VRE operators can manage Virtual Machines or managed Kubernetes clusters that support the execution of container-based applications. For uniform deployment and facilitating the migration from one federated provider to another, for those Analytics Computing Framework components (JupyterHub and Galaxy) designed to run on Kubernetes, Kubernetes is deployed on top of the OpenStack resources. This architecture allows for the expansion of the resources available to the Blue-Cloud VRE on multiple providers without changing the provider configuration nor imposing additional requirements on them while keeping the user experience consistent across the federation.

² <https://jupyter.org/hub>

³ <https://galaxyproject.org/>

Third party services are integrated using IAM integration without entering into the details of the underlying supporting infrastructure. Optionally these services can be deployed on the available OpenStack or Kubernetes resources after agreement with the VRE operators.

1.2. Implementation Strategies within the VRE

1.2.1. Federation of Kubernetes providers

Kubernetes is a portable, extensible, open-source platform for managing containerized workloads and services, that facilitates both declarative configuration and automation. Kubernetes can be considered the de-facto standard for container-based application management, thanks to its wide support for running on every major cloud provider and on premises setups. Kubernetes abstracts the underlying hardware in a uniform way, making it possible to deploy applications on disparate infrastructures without any changes.

The Analytics Computing Framework deployment on Kubernetes requires:

- Kubernetes version 1.23 or later
- Support for the Kubernetes Ingress objects is provided. An ingress allows mapping external traffic to different backends based on rules.
- Support for the creation of shared volumes that can be accessed by several pods (a pod is the basic scheduling unit for Kubernetes, and is composed of one or more containers with shared computing, network and storage resources). NFS is a possible technology for supporting these volumes.
- Allow the usage of fuse⁴ for mounting the user's workspace.

1.2.1.1. Dataspaces

Each of the available clusters from different e-infrastructure providers will support one or multiple VREs. Before deploying the services, the Blue-Cloud VRE operators will create a set of dataspace volumes, depending on the VREs to be supported. These are available as a Kubernetes Persistent Volume Claim and will be available for all the applications running on the cluster and supporting the VRE. The below shows a sample definition of a 1TB dataspace volume for Blue-Cloud:

```
apiVersion: v1
kind: PersistentVolumeClaim
metadata:
  name: blue-cloud-dataspace
spec:
  accessModes:
    - ReadWriteMany
  resources:
```

⁴ <https://github.com/libfuse/libfuse>

```
requests:
  storage: 1000Gi
storageClassName: nfs-client
volumeMode: Filesystem
```

Any application running on the Kubernetes cluster will be able to access the volumes to provide a shared space where users belonging to a given VLab can contribute to.

Figure 2 – Dataspace volume mounting by VRE services

1.2.1.2. Federation through JupyterHub

JupyterHub⁵ is a multi-user environment managing access to computational environments and resources within a user-friendly interface. Originally designed to support the execution of Jupyter⁶, its customisation options allow for the on-demand execution of a large set of interactive applications running on various types of infrastructure, from personal laptops to HPC clusters.

JupyterHub architecture is shown in Figure 3. JupyterHub is a set of processes that together, provide a single-user Jupyter Notebook server for each person in a group. There are three main subsystems:

⁵ <https://jupyter.org/hub>

⁶ <https://jupyter.org/>

Figure 3 – JupyterHub in Blue-Cloud 2026

- Hub: manages user accounts, authentication, and coordinates Single User Notebook Servers. Different authenticators control access to JupyterHub and the Spawner controls how JupyterHub starts the individual notebook server for each user.
- Proxy: the public-facing part of JupyterHub that uses a dynamic proxy to route HTTP requests to the Hub and Single User Notebook Servers.
- Single-User Notebook Server: a dedicated, single-user, Jupyter Notebook server is started for each user on the system when the user logs in.

In the case of Blue-Cloud, the JupyterHub is customized with a D4Science authenticator and a D4Science spawner. Both are available in GitHub⁷.

The D4Science authenticator performs authentication of the users with the D4Science IAM. Besides authentication, it also performs authorization by checking the user membership to the VREs and will dynamically configure the availability of environments and dataspace for the users by querying the D4Science Information System. The D4Science spawner creates Single-User Notebooks servers on Kubernetes ensuring the configuration of the access to the appropriate dataspace.

⁷ <https://github.com/EGI-federation/egi-notebooks-hub>

JupyterHub is used to manage two types of environments:

- Native Jupyter Notebooks with Python, Julia and R, with different library environments as requested by the VRE users.
- Proxied applications through the Jupyter server proxy extension⁸, such as RStudio and Pluto.jl. This extension allows for any interactive application that can be containerised and that uses HTTP to be accessed as part of the Jupyter session without any modification.

New applications can be easily added given the following constraints:

- Applications need to be packaged as a set of docker containers running as non-root user. Several containers can be run in parallel (i.e. sidecar containers).
- Alongside the application, the main docker container for the application must have the JupyterHub, Jupyter and Jupyter-server-proxy python libraries installed. Within a working python environment, this can be achieved with:
 - `pip install jupyterhub jupyter jupyter-server-proxy`
- A configuration for jupyter-server-proxy so the application can be started when the container is started as described in the documentation⁹.

JupyterHub takes care of starting an instance of the applications for every individual user, ensuring they run isolated without interfering with each other. The dataspace is mounted and made available to applications in the expected location.

When a user logs into the system a Server Options page will be shown (see Figure 4) so the user can select the most appropriate for his/her needs. The list of options is dynamically created by querying the D4Science Information System and checking the permissions received from IAM upon authentication.

⁸ <https://github.com/jupyterhub/jupyter-server-proxy>

⁹ <https://jupyter-server-proxy.readthedocs.io/en/latest/server-process.html>

Figure 4 – Server Options

Each JupyterHub available for a given user on a VRE is easily accessible via the top menu of the VRE (Figure 5). For each of the e-infrastructure there is a Start (to create the Notebook server) and a Stop (to stop a running Notebook server) so users can easily access and manage resources from different infrastructures in a seamless way.

Figure 5 – Jupyter menu in the VRE

Other non-Jupyter applications can be made available in a similar way; for example, RStudio menu will show Start and Stop options for each of the available e-infrastructures. From the deployment point of view there is no need to have separate JupyterHub instances and RStudio and JupyterLab are managed in the same way, only differing on the set of Server Options shown to the user which will be determined by the context of the user when reaching the hub available from the Information System and the information received from IAM.

Figure 6 – Rstudio Server Options

1.2.1.3. Federation through Galaxy

Galaxy is a scientific workflow platform that aims to make computational workflows accessible to research scientists that do not have computer programming or systems administration experience. Although it was initially developed for genomics research, it is largely domain agnostic and is now used as a general workflow management system. Galaxy is a complex web-based application mostly written in python with a web-based user interface. With a drag and drop interface, users can execute single tools or a set of tools in a workflow from the browser. Galaxy can use a wide variety of backends for executing those tools, ensuring that the tools are invoked with the right input and that the output is made back available in the platform. In the case of the Blue-Cloud VRE, Galaxy is deployed using (1) a main Galaxy server pod that runs the Galaxy code for managing the platform; (2) a shared PVC where the data files are persisted and shared between all the Galaxy jobs, and (3) Galaxy tools job that are spawned whenever the users triggers the execution of a workflow. These jobs share access to the Galaxy PVC so they can easily read input data and produce output data. Galaxy takes care of ensuring each job can only access the files it is entitled to access. With this architecture, Galaxy can scale to run as many jobs in parallel as resources are available in the Kubernetes cluster as each job can run independently.

1.2.2. Federation of OpenStack

OpenStack is an open-source cloud computing platform used to build and manage public and private cloud infrastructures. It provides a set of software tools to help organizations set up and manage cloud services like computing, networking, storage, and more, all within their own data centres or across a distributed environment. OpenStack essentially provides the infrastructure-as-a-service (IaaS) layer for cloud computing. In the case of Blue-Cloud, OpenStack is used to start Virtual Machines where the Analytics Computing Framework components can be deployed. There are three main ways OpenStack is exploited within the VRE:

1. Deployment of JupyterHub/Galaxy and other Kubernetes-based applications. In this case a Kubernetes cluster is set up on top of the OpenStack. This allows for a uniform management of the applications and easy migration between providers.
2. Deployment of the Cloud Compute Platform (CCP). CCP uses containers through Docker Swarm, which can be executed on top of generic VMs delivered by OpenStack.
3. Deployment of third-party applications directly on VMs. Especially suited for the "lift and shift" approach of moving applications to the cloud, where the application is migrated from an on-premises setup to a cloud infrastructure with minimal changes or re-architecting. The application is packaged as a VM and executed on OpenStack without additional changes.

1.2.2.1. Setup of Kubernetes clusters on OpenStack

If a provider does not deliver a managed Kubernetes ready to be used by D4Science, the Blue-Cloud VRE operators can set-up a working Kubernetes cluster on top of OpenStack or bare-metal resources. The hardware requirements are as follows:

1. One master node with at least 2 cores, 8GB of RAM and 100 GB of disk space. The master should not be exposed to the public internet.
2. One NFS node with at least 2 cores, 8GB of RAM and disk space to host the shared dataspace and user homes. The disk space will depend on the amount and size of dataspace and the number of users to support in this cluster.
3. A set of worker nodes with at least 8 cores, 16 GB of RAM and 500GB of disk space (disk space is used to store the container images) where the actual workloads will be run. One of these nodes (called ingress node) should be accessible through ports 80 and 443 to the public internet so it can be reached by the users.

A Terraform¹⁰ configuration template for creating these nodes on OpenStack providers is available in GitHub¹¹.

Once the nodes are available, they are configured with ansible, which will take care of:

- Configure ssh access for the operators of the Kubernetes cluster
- Installing and configuring Kubernetes on the available nodes
- Installing and configuring NFS so it can be used for the creation of the volumes
- Installing a NGINX-based ingress for exposing the applications installed on top of Kubernetes, and assigning to it the public IP of the ingress node
- Installing cert-manager for the automated retrieval of SSL certificates for the applications running on Kubernetes
- Installing prometheus and grafana for the monitoring of the nodes of the cluster

1.2.3. Federation through CCP

The Cloud Computing Platform (CCP) is natively designed in a distributed and federation oriented way. As shown in the following figure showing its logical architecture, CCP is composed of its functional core and a set of Controllers that interface CCP with its execution infrastructures. The CCP Core runs as a Docker stack on the D4Science Docker swarm cluster hosted on ISTI OpenStack infrastructure. The Controllers are components that logically act on behalf of CCP but can be deployed in different ways depending on the communication patterns they use for interacting with the controlled execution infrastructure.

¹⁰ <https://www.terraform.io/>

¹¹ <https://github.com/EGI-Federation/notebooks/tree/main/template/terraform>

Figure 7 – CCP Logical Architecture

The rationale behind this architectural design is that it must be possible to run methods and algorithms on CCP from as many other platforms as possible and it must be possible to incrementally federate as many heterogeneous execution infrastructures as possible.

In order to provide different execution infrastructures several controllers have been built and others are ongoing or possible candidates as shown in the following picture.

Figure 8 – Developed, planned and possible CCP execution infrastructures

Docker-swarm controller enables Docker swarm clusters to become execution infrastructures for methods packed in Docker containers. The native D4Science Production and Development clusters are the primary, native execution infrastructures of CCP. In the case of the natively supported infrastructures the controller is deployed tightly coupled with CCP core on the same resources.

In addition, a plain **Docker controller** has been developed in order to allow the adoption of personal PCs and laptops as execution infrastructures. This is especially useful for onboarding developers of CCP itself or to verify the possibility to run GPU based methods. Instances of these controllers are usually deployed locally onto the user’s hardware.

A **Galaxy controller** has been added in order to be able to run Galaxy tools and workflows as CCP methods. This controller can be deployed on D4Science resources and it interacts with the Galaxy instance it controls through Galaxy REST API calls. The controller has been tested with Galaxy instances provided by D4Science and with usegalaxy.eu.

Currently, the D4Science developers are implementing **Kubernetes controllers**. These controllers will be able to run CCP methods encapsulated inside Docker containers also on Kubernetes controlled resources. Kubernetes infrastructures will be made available natively by D4Science as described in earlier sections.

During meetings with Blue-Cloud2026 partners, other ideas have emerged and there are plans to at least evaluate and document possible implementations for running CCP controlled methods on top of more HPC oriented platforms such as **Singularity** clusters or **SLURM** managed clusters.

As described before, another idea of federating CCP is based on the possibility to run CCP methods from as many platforms as possible. This interoperability is possible by the design of a standards based REST API (OGC Processes 1.1) to request method execution. Any authorized user or software can interact with CCP in order to get access to the list of methods, request their execution and monitor it.

Supporting tools like code generators have been made available to further ease the work for users.

It's now possible to run CCP methods from Bash, Python, Julia and R code or from platforms like JupyterHub and R-Studio.

A generic CCP method executor has been integrated in Galaxy in order to execute any CCP method by simply providing a request data structure (that can be easily generated with a click). In addition, CCP methods can be exported and imported into Galaxy instances as specialized tools on their own and then become part of workflows.

Figure 9 – CCP methods in Galaxy

Generic Galaxy 24 Tool

A Generic Galaxy 24 tool execution

Inputs

- * Runtime
The image of the runtime to use for method execution. This depends on the infrastructure specific protocol for interacting with registries.
- * Tool ID
The ID of the tool to execute on the Galaxy 24 infrastructure
- * Tool version
The version of the tool to be executed
- * API key
Your API key created for the Galaxy 24 infrastructure
- * Resource type
Either tool or Workflow
- * ID of history
The id of a history otherwise a new one will be created
- * Annotations for execution
The value of this parameter will be associated as annotation to the execution

Figure 10 – Running a Galaxy tool from CCP

Another activity that has been carried out is the integration of HEU **iImagine project**¹² containers for AI based algorithms. Two methods have been integrated (deephdc/deep-oc-plants-classification-tf and ai4oshub/ai4os-image-classification-tf) and a workflow for partially automating the process has been sketched.

¹² <https://www.imagine-ai.eu/>

Figure 11 – iMagine methods integrated in CCP

2. Federated infrastructures

This section describes the current federated infrastructures available through the VRE and the end-user services running on them: Google Cloud Platform supporting JupyterHub and Galaxy; and EGI Cloud Compute at INFN-Bari supporting webODV.

2.1. Google Cloud Platform

Google Cloud Platform (GCP) is a suite of cloud computing services offered by Google. It provides a wide range of infrastructure, platform, and software services for computing, storage, networking, machine learning, and more. Google Kubernetes Engine (GKE) is a managed Kubernetes service provided by GCP that simplifies the deployment, management, and scaling of containerized applications. GKE removes much of the operational overhead of managing Kubernetes clusters by automating tasks such as cluster upgrades, health monitoring, and security patching.

In the context of Blue-Cloud, two GKE Kubernetes clusters are available for the federation of resources in the VRE: one for production usage and a second one for testing and development purposes. These clusters are set with auto-scaling, so they automatically scale the number of nodes in a cluster and dynamically allocate resources based on workload demands. Figure 12 shows the GCP dashboard for the production environment.

Figure 12 – GCP Console

In order to deploy Jupyterhub in GKE, some of the configuration was tuned to adapt to the new environment:

- User applications (the single-user servers) are created in different Kubernetes namespaces for better control of the consumption of resources as each namespace can be configured independently with specific quotas and limits.
- Applications are exposed through the native GKE ingress and load balancer instead of the NGINX-Ingress used in other deployments.
- Dataspaces are created on Google Filestore, a fully managed network-attached storage system that can be attached as volumes in GKE Kubernetes clusters.
- Container images for the applications are stored in Google Artifact Registry for faster access from the nodes of the cluster (see Figure 13)

The screenshot shows the Google Cloud Artifact Registry interface. At the top, the breadcrumb navigation indicates the path: europe-west4-docker.pkg.dev > d4science-prod-vre-prj > d4science-prod-images. The 'Repository Details' section shows the format as 'Docker' and the type as 'Standard'. Below this is a table of images with columns for Name, Connection, Created, and Updated. The table lists several images, including 'hub', 'rstudio-d4science', and various 'single-user' images.

<input type="checkbox"/>	Name ↑	Connection	Created	Updated
<input type="checkbox"/>	hub	–	Jan 31, 2024	Feb 20, 2024
<input type="checkbox"/>	rstudio-d4science	–	Apr 26, 2024	8 days ago
<input type="checkbox"/>	single-user-d4science	–	Feb 6, 2024	9 days ago
<input type="checkbox"/>	single-user-pluto-d4science	–	Oct 24, 2024	Oct 24, 2024
<input type="checkbox"/>	single-user-r-d4science	–	Feb 7, 2024	9 days ago
<input type="checkbox"/>	single-user-sobigdata	–	Feb 6, 2024	9 days ago
<input type="checkbox"/>	single-user-sobigdata-aaai24	–	Feb 20, 2024	Feb 20, 2024

Figure 13 – Google Artifact Registry

Currently the production cluster supports a JupyterHub installation and two Galaxy installations for Blue-Cloud and the Marine Omics VLab. This cluster is configured to use a node pool where each node has 20 CPU cores and 70 GB of RAM with autoscaling so new nodes will be created on the fly whenever the load. Figure 14 shows the list of nodes available in the pool.

Figure 14 – Node pools in production cluster

2.2. EGI Cloud Compute - INFN Bari

EGI Cloud Compute is a multi-cloud service that offers access to OpenStack providers to run Virtual Machines on demand with complete control over computing resources. EGI Cloud Compute gives you the ability to deploy and scale virtual machines on-demand. It offers guaranteed computational resources in a secure and isolated environment with standard API access, without the overhead of managing physical servers. INFN-Bari is one of the EGI's resource centres that contribute computing power, storage, and other resources to the EGI Cloud Compute Service.

Blue-Cloud-2026 has established a Service Level Agreement between EGI and the project to define the provision and support of the services listed in the Table below.

Resource Center	Cloud Compute	Online Storage
-----------------	---------------	----------------

INFN-Bari	32 vCPU cores, 32 GB RAM, Floating IPs available, 200 GB of SSD storage	25 TB
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Table 1 – EGI Cloud Compute allocation at INFN-Bari

These resources are used to deploy a webODV instance for Blue-Cloud VRE users with access to large ocean datasets from the global Argo program and the SeaDataNet infrastructure. Figure 15 shows the OpenStack overview dashboard for the allocated resources at the provider.

Figure 15 – OpenStack dashboard at INFN-Bari

A single VM with all the available capacity runs webODV through Docker compose at the site and available as part of the VRE offer as shown in Figure 16.

Figure 16 – webODV in Blue-Cloud Lab

3. Conclusions and future plans

This document has described the current federation model and approaches to leverage resources from different resources providers within the Blue-Cloud VRE so users can run workloads already supported by the Analytics Computing Framework and access new applications from remote providers in a seamless and integrated way with the rest of the VRE. The federation relies on industry standard platforms for delivering access to computing resources: OpenStack and Kubernetes. These are available at multiple providers, both commercial and institutional, and in case they are not directly available, Kubernetes can be deployed on most of the existing resource providers, including on-premises resources.

There are three main approaches for the federation:

- Using JupyterHub, deployed on top of Kubernetes resources (either from managed Kubernetes offers or Kubernetes deployed on OpenStack by the VRE operators), to offer access to single-user interactive applications, with a focus on Notebooks-like applications like Jupyter and RStudio.
- Using Galaxy, deployed on top of Kubernetes as well, for the execution of workflows
- Using CCP, which has a pluggable architecture to provide different execution infrastructures, and currently supports Docker-swarm and Galaxy as execution platform.

Additionally, third party applications can be incorporated into the VRE through the integration with the Identity and Access Management (IAM) component to ensure a common identity and authorization for the VRE users.

Currently the federation has been established by incorporating two new infrastructures: Google Cloud Platform, where JupyterHub and Galaxy are available to the users, and EGI Cloud Compute, where webODV is deployed and integrated as well.

For the next period, the project will focus on expanding the federated infrastructures covering resources or services delivered by WEKEO, EUDAT and JERICO-CORE. For each of these infrastructures, we will determine the best method for federating the available resources based on their capabilities (e.g. availability of Kubernetes).

The CCP will be extended as well to support Kubernetes controllers to facilitate the integration of Kubernetes-based resources as platform for running users' methods. Support for SLURM and Singularity may also be implemented depending on the capabilities of the target infrastructures.

References

- [1] M. Assante, L. Candela, D. Castelli, R. Cirillo, G. Coro, L. Frosini, L. Lelii, F. Mangiacrapa, P. Pagano, G. Panichi, F. Sinibaldi *Enacting open science by D4Science*. (2019) Future Gener. Comput. Syst. 101: 555-563 [10.1016/j.future.2019.05.063](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.future.2019.05.063)
- [2] M. Assante, L. Candela, D. Castelli, R. Cirillo, G. Coro, A. Dell'Amico, L. Frosini, L. Lelii, F. Mangiacrapa, P. Pagano, G. Panichi, F. Sinibaldi (2023) *Virtual research environments co-creation: The D4Science experience*. Concurrency Computat Pract Exper. 2023; 35(18): e6925. doi:[10.1002/cpe.6925](https://doi.org/10.1002/cpe.6925)
- [3] M. Assante, L. Candela, D. Castelli, R. Cirillo, G. Coro, L. Frosini, L. Lelii, F. Mangiacrapa, V. Marioli, P. Pagano, G. Panichi, C. Perciante, F. Sinibaldi (2019) *The gCube system: Delivering Virtual Research Environments as-a-Service*. Future Gener. Comput. Syst. 95: 445-453 [10.1016/j.future.2018.10.035](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.future.2018.10.035)